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Emotional and Psychological Consequences of AI in Daily Life: A Qualitative Study

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Abstract

The psychological and emotional effects of artificial intelligence (AI), which is becoming more and more integrated into daily life, are still unclear. The emotional and psychological effects of interacting with modern AI technologies, especially generative and adaptive systems, are investigated in this qualitative study. Twenty current AI users participated in semi-structured interviews using a phenomenological design from a variety of educational and occupational backgrounds. Thematic analysis proposed by Braun and Clarke was used to analyse the data and code and meaning saturation were methodically recorded. Four main themes surfaced: (1) positive experiences of increased productivity, decreased cognitive load and emotional fulfilment; (2) negative psychological effects, including emotional disruption, reliance, a decline in critical thinking and anxiety related to one's work; (3) functional and ethical issues with data misuse, privacy and exposure to damaging or incorrect content; and (4) broad attitudes influenced by perceived user responsibility, normalization and low awareness. AI Empower support as well as psychological distress so, ethical considerations and human wellbeing should be prioritized while designing AI tools. Emotional impact should be examined by policy makers, mental health professionals and developers so that AI integrated safely and sustainably. how our emotions are affected by AI, shown in this valuable and evidence-based study that can create a more responsible development in mental health care.

Keywords. Artificial Intelligence, Emotional Well-being, Human–AI Interaction, Psychological Impact, Qualitative Research, Technology Adoption.

Introduction

In today's technologically advanced society, artificial intelligence (AI) has become widespread and is being integrated into many facets of human existence (Russell & Norvig, 2021). The growing prevalence of AI-based systems in daily lives of the individuals raises significant questions about how and to what extent these technologies impact emotions of its users (Shneiderman, 2020). Artificial intelligence (AI) in this study refers to software programs that are capable of performing tasks that require human-like cognitive abilities, such as learning, reasoning and content creation. Recommendation algorithms that impact

emotions, thoughts and choices of the users were highlighted along with generative big language models (like ChatGPT) and automated content production tools. Digital systems that are rule-based and non-adaptive, such as search engines and basic automation, were not included. This operational description of AI aligns with the objective of study investigating the psychological and affective impacts of interactive and adaptive AI systems (Chen et al., 2024). Researchers have deeply probed the ethics, sociology and technical dimensions of IT, but they have accorded relatively less priority to the psychological and emotional impact of IT on particular users until now, especially with qualitative methodologies for research studies like this one. (Araujo et al., 2020). By concentrating on the subjective experiences of the people with IT, the aim of this research is to throw some light on these complex phenomena. The emphasis on personal experiences can be useful for gaining further insight not only into the particular impact of IT on emotional health but also into the complex conceptual environment surrounding the interface between human users and machinery.

Previous research has uncovered that if the systems display anthropomorphic traits, they tend to cause human astonishment, discomfort or confusion and this has several ethical and social implications (Shank et al., 2019). The primary goal of developing AI systems is to design machines that have the ability to mimic cognitive functions of individuals such as learning, reasoning and self-correcting process (Russell and Norvig, 2021). This action embodies the intelligence defined as a set of functions such as adaptation, improvement, which can potentially be put into machines (Poole et al., 1998). Historically, technology-based tools such as computers, robots, etc. have been used to enhance human capabilities such as strength (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014) and today, AI technology is seen as an extension of intellectual capabilities using computer technology (Rich & Knight, 1991). However, AI remains a domain characterized by diversity (Fetzer & J. H., 1990). The focus has then shifted to views and methodological debates, mainly about: Engineering of intelligent machines that can operate with human-like autonomy and reasoning (McCarthy, 2007; Ertel & W., 2018).

The construct of emotional health refers to capability to acknowledge, regulate and effectively communicate emotions of the individuals in ways that promote overall well-being. It Resilience to challenges of life, the capability to cultivate meaningful relationships and coping adaptively with change. The World Health Organization continues to define emotional health as the ability to maintain emotional balance and life satisfaction by recognizing and regulating their emotions themselves (WHO, 2005). Emotional intelligence defines the competence of recognizing and regulating individual's own emotions and the emotions of others. Being emotionally healthy intricately connects to productivity as people with higher emotional intelligence demonstrate improved capacity to manage stress, care for mental health and navigate social complexities in an efficient way (Mayer et al., 2016). The model of Daniel Goleman encompasses skills like motivational, self-regulation and empathic and interpersonal effectiveness skills which are the basis of underlying adaptive functioning and resilience (Goleman, 1995).

A critical study of the literature indicates a significant positive relationship between increased emotional intelligence and subjective happiness and reduced incidence of anxiety and depression (Sánchez-Álvarez et al., 2016). The impact of AI on emotional health and wellness encompasses a range of scenarios, including both beneficial outcomes and adverse effects (Araujo et al., 2020). Study associates the adoption of AI with improvements in productivity and satisfaction in the realm of both work and education. (Dwivedi et al., 2021). On the other hand, over-reliance on AI tools raises issues with job displacement, reduced cognitive capacity and increased social isolation caused by virtual communication, alongside major privacy concerns regarding personal data on the Internet (Jobin et al., 2019). The aggregate effect of all these variables can trigger emotional distress among users (König & Mehrotra, 2025). Accordingly, it is important to carefully manage the integration of AI technology in order to maximize benefits and limit potential risks (Floridi & Cowls, 2022).

Rationale

As humans increasingly integrate artificial intelligence (AI) technology into daily life, it has impacts not only as a tool but also as a technology affecting emotional and psychological well-being of the AI users. Despite extensive debate on AI and its implications on a variety of dimensions, one of the greatest gaps of understanding pertains to its complex nature. Regarding the psychological and emotional experiences of

users while using AI systems, existing studies have traditionally paid much attention to efficiency. However, it appears that researchers have given little attention to the subjective point of view with respect to the impact of AI on psychology and emotions (Araujo et al., 2020). Previous literature tends to emphasize the implications of AI regarding the impact it could have on user autonomy, decision-making or mental health. Automating human tasks and relying on AI suggestions rather than human discretion, can cause decision fatigue, helplessness and reduced critical thinking (Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2019; Schiff, 2022). These effects could undercut perceptions of individual , especially if AI systems are opaque or if addicting interactive patterns, such as autoplay and infinite scroll, are present. (Lukoff et al., 2021). Furthermore, algorithmic bias not only poses medical concerns but also creates intense ethical and emotional issues, damaging communities and widening the gap of distrust and alienation (Caliskan et al., 2017; Buolamwini & Gebru, 2018; Liu, 2024).

Adding to these challenges, users frequently confront privacy concerns, social isolation from over-reliance on virtual communication tools, identity-related anxiety and cognitive overload (Jobin et al., 2019; König & Mehrotra, 2025; Chandra et al., 2024). These factors add up to emotional distress that quantitative models seldom capture but qualitative inquiry into lived experience reveals the importance of place vividly. The literature also claims that promoting AI literacy, ethical awareness and educational interventions act as protective factor as it provides the user with the psychological readiness to engage critically and autonomously with AI tools (Schiff, 2022; Ateeq et al., 2024).

This study is important because it addressed the urgent need to fill empirical and conceptual gaps regarding the emotional and psychological implications of AI use in daily life. The study adopted a qualitative phenomenological research methodology focused on subjective experiences of users of AI. This study explored the affective and cognitive dynamics that traditional quantitative and theoretical approaches have overlooked. This is a crucial aspect of ensuring that AI developers, policymakers and mental health professionals understand how to develop these systems to improve human well-being and reduce psychological risks.

This rationale emphasized the need for further development of interdisciplinary and morally informed and psychologically-sensitive AI research that emphasize the values of the autonomy, transparency and emotional well-being of AI users as primary objectives within the developing AI symbiosis.

Objective

The purpose of this research work was to examine how an individual perceives the emotional and implications of using Artificial Intelligence software.

Research Question

How do individuals perceive the emotional and psychological effects of using Artificial Intelligence tools?

Research Methodology

Participants

Twenty participants aged 18 to 30 were chosen through stratified purposive sampling. Sampling to ensure that there is heterogeneity in terms of academic and/or professional backgrounds, including areas such as education, technology, marketing and management. The participants were expected to be active users of AI tool use in academic or professional settings. People with substantive physical or mental health issues, as well as individuals whose human-AI interaction was limited to passive social media use, were excluded. Data collection went on in an iterative manner and collections followed the principle of thematic saturation. Saturation was determined at two levels: code saturation where no new codes were generated and meaning saturation where no new conceptual ideas were developed. It was found that after 17 interviews, no new codes were found and after 20 interviews, new data codes were not being generated. Saturation was recorded with a saturation grid was established during the entire process of data analysis and the recruitment stage was stopped once the code and meaning saturation was achieved.

Data Collection

Recruitment involved electronic communication as well as personal communication, leading to informed methods of obtaining consent emphasizing confidentiality, voluntariness and the right to withdraw from the study at any stage of the research. Semi-structured interviews, lasting around 20-30 minutes, took place in

a quiet and comfortable setting in order to facilitate reflective thinking. All the interviews were recorded with the consent of the participant and supplemented by the observational notes of the researcher to capture contextual cues.

Interview Guide

The interview guide was designed based on existing literature and grounded in Self-Determination Theory (Deci and Ryan, 1985) and incorporated inquiries into perception of AI, emotional reactions, autonomy and social influence. The interview guide was expert-reviewed and pilot-tested to refine clarity, order and conceptual emphasis.

Reflexivity

During the whole process of data gathering, the researcher maintained a reflexive practice to acknowledge and work with their personal biases, emotional reactions and subjective influences. In instances where moments of disagreement or emotional responses were observed during interviews, the researcher made it a point to reflect on such instances before regaining composure, which helped the researcher to remain objective position. This thoughtful self-awareness and critical examination promoted the authenticity and trustworthiness of data gathering or the quality and validity of the research data collected.

Data Analysis

The transcripts of the interviews were manually analysed using a thematic framework developed by Braun & Clarke (2006). The coding started with coding of the themes by completing one introductory round of coding followed by iterations of themes. Coding decisions were corroborated by three independent researchers to enhance analytic reliability. Trustworthiness was further supported through the criteria proposed by Guba and Lincoln (1981) which including credibility (member checking, peer debriefing), transferability (rich descriptions of context and participants), dependability (audit trails) and confirmability (reflexive journaling and documentation). Saturation was confirmed during analysis when successive transcripts no longer produced new codes or meaning-level insights.

Results

Figure 1: Themes with their respective codes.

Theme 1: Positive Perceptions and Benefits of AI

Code	Quote	Participants
Beneficial	It is beneficial	P3, P7
Time-saving	It is Time saving	P2, P5, P10
Reduced cognitive load	It limits the cognitive load	P8, P11
Satisfaction	It enhances satisfaction	P7, P1
Joyful feelings	I feel joyful, / it makes me happy	P9, P4, P 11
Academic convenience	It reduces manual work	P6, P 12, P4

Theme 2: Emotional and Psychological Impact

Code	Quote	Participants
Emotional disturbance	It creates emotional disturbance	P5, P13
Mental disturbance	It creates mental disturbance	P6, P15
Cognitive effect	It affects our cognitive ability It affects our thinking	P8, P16
Emotional distress	It creates emotional distress when not getting the desired response	P9, P17
Job anxiety	Due to AI there is job displacement from human to robots causing job anxiety	P11, P19
Addiction & dependency	It makes people addicted Dependency on anything other than yourself is dangerous”	P7, P18

Theme 3: Ethical and Functional Concerns

Code	Quote	Participants
Privacy concerns	It collects and stores users personal data that can be misused	P2, P13
Misuse of data	Misuse of data becomes easy	P5, P12
Harassment risk	It can edit pics easily that can be used for harassment	P8, P14
Vulgar/negative content	It provides vulgar content that we admire unintentionally	P16
Manipulation	It can manipulate the way we think if overused	P6, P17
Accuracy doubts	It provides content that may not be correct	P10, P18

Theme 4: General Attitudes Toward AI

Code	Quote	Participants
No effect	There is no effect on us as Pakistanis There is no influence	P3, P20
Neutral/normal use	Layman will take it normal Nowadays no feeling	P4, P15, P18

Code	Quote	Participants
Lack of awareness	Normally people are not aware of it	P7, P12
Control/responsibility	It's up to you to control software rather than they control you	P13, P19
Normalization	Everyone's using it, so I did too	P9, P14

Discussion

This study offers a very perceptive insight into the complexities involved in the manner in which individuals emotionally and psychologically interact with the AI technology in their lives. Four important themes that emerged from the thematic analysis include the positive attitudes and advantages AI technology induced. This study demonstrates the benefits of AI technology. The narrative below explores the psychological effects along with moral and practical implications and public attitudes towards AI. Researchers contextualize these findings within established psychological theories and prior empirical research to illustrate how AI functions dually as an enabling resource and a cause of distress for users.

Often, the attendees identified the positive aspects of Artificial Intelligence as saving time, increase satisfaction and alleviate cognitive burden and these positive experiences correlate heavily with Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985) which argues that human flourishing is based on the satisfaction of basic psychological needs such as relatedness, competence and autonomy. Experts view AI as having augmented competence through simplifying tasks in academics, reducing cognitive load and facilitating quick information access. This lends evidence to existing literature that suggests a sense of power and control over technology by the user, Personalized AI can thus greatly enhance productivity as well as subjective well-being (Pedreschi et al., 2023).

On the other hand, several respondents exhibited elements of dependence, confusion and psychological distress, particularly with regards to being confronted with misleading AI outcomes or being inundated with information. Such results are understandable through the Cognitive Load Theory lens (Sweller, Kawski 1988), the "overload" phenomenon, where too much information obstructs cognitive processing. Further, the concept of "learned helplessness" propounded by Seligman (1972) gives meaning to symptoms of addiction and reduction in cognitive functions such as problem-solving capacities, wherein the presence of possible continued external control may decrease self-efficacy and autonomy. Past research supports these kinds of negative psychological experiences and suggests a possible connection. Consequently, this method improves critical thinking skills and autonomy. Participant feedback commonly mentioned ethical and functional considerations, particularly regarding violations of privacy, misuse and exposure to harmful content. These topics resonate with wider concerns that scholars have documented in the literature on algorithmic bias and digital surveillance. (Caliskan et al., 2017), which emphasizes the disproportionate psychological toll exacted from marginalized. Populations affected by untransparent or discriminatory AI systems.

From the point of view of the Trust and Technology theoretical framework, Doubt of participants was discovered to express Further intensified in the South Asian cultural setting where digital literacy is not homogenous and emerging regulatory frameworks (Luhmann, 1979).

It is relevant to note that a portion of the participants held indifferent and normalized feelings about AI, seeing it merely as a common gadget or social norm. This corresponds to Technology Acceptance Model, by Davis (Davis, 1989), Users have embraced and adopted the technology despite risks, motivated by its perceived usefulness and social influence. But such a normalizing process was normally followed by a deferral of responsibility to the user of the technology ("it's up to you to control it"), which suggests a cultural pattern of acceptance that may cover a critical evaluation of the possible dangers of AI.

In conclusion, the results demonstrate the double-edged role of AI in that, on the one hand productivity and satisfaction, although it involves high psychological risks related to fostering dependency, spreading misinformation and cultivating moral ambiguity. The Self-Determination Theory, Cognitive Load Theory, Learned Helplessness, sociotechnical Models around trust and acceptance offer a strong theoretical

explanation for the above conflicting experiences of AI user. Pakistani socio-cultural environment and variability in digital literacy skills also mediate variability in attitudes and emotional experiences.

Implications of the Research Findings

The given research contains a set of crucial implications such as it highlights the dynamics of AI usage, especially emphasizing the roles of anxiety, dependency and satisfaction in user experiences. Such observations underscore the importance of developers creating and implementing AI with a consideration of their psychological effects. This study will "concrete recommendations for ethical AI development, including the importance of ensuring "privacy, transparency and protection of user welfare. This ties in with growing demands for providing accountable artificial intelligence design and suggests various lessons for designers and policymakers. These findings also suggest that there is a need for literacy in AI and education in the use of AI, to empower individuals with the abilities to critically, independently think and engage with the technology of AI. These might include: promote more well-balanced and healthier relationships between humans and AI.

Further, there is an indication of balanced integration of AI in order to optimize productivity policy frameworks that aim to reap the maximum benefits from technology without harming the human well-being. Finally, the findings that can be derived from this study will be able to help policymakers and educators in guiding and developers in building user-centered AI systems and shaping AI decisions deployment in education, training and other social systems. By stressing both deployment and concerning their practical applications and ethical implications, the above-mentioned results contribute to discussions on the effects of applied AI on the real world.

Limitations

This paper recognizes that possible bias in the selection process imposes limitations, as well as the use of data and the limits of generalization implicit within qualitative research.

Recommendations

Future studies should try to include more diverse respondents, combine methodologies and conduct longitudinal studies to better understand changing user experiences. Increased AI literacy and ethics education are imperative in creating a knowledgeable engagement and responsible policy development.

Conclusion

This study shows that integrating artificial intelligence appears to enhance productivity and satisfaction, while simultaneously posing issues related to privacy, autonomy and critical thinking. To effectively address these issues, there is a need to adopt ethical standards.

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